

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL HASEEB bearing USN 6SU20AO001 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADRIKA K bearing USN 6SU20AO002 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AGNAS TREESA JINNY bearing USN 6SU20AO003 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AKSHAY DEV T bearing USN 6SU20AO004 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJAL P bearing USN 6SU20AO005 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANJU JOHNSON bearing USN 6SU20AO006 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ANUSREE C S bearing USN 6SU20AO007 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN KUMAR N P bearing USN 6SU20AO008 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWIN P bearing USN 6SU20AO009 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms GLADYS ANN REJI bearing USN 6SU20AO010 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JACOB JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU20AO011 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JINSY WILSON bearing USN 6SU20AO012 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JITHIN J LAL bearing USN 6SU20AO013 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOSHY JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU20AO014 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MAHITHA MANIKANDAN bearing USN 6SU20AO015 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MARIYAMATH MURSHIDA M A bearing USN 6SU20AO016 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMED FASIR T P M bearing USN 6SU20AO017 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms MOHAMMED SHIHAS K.S. bearing USN 6SU20AO018 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAKHIL PRASAD P P bearing USN 6SU20AO019 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NAVYA P bearing USN 6SU20AO020 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NIKITA GANGADHAR NAIK bearing USN 6SU20AO021 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms NUF AIS RAHMAN K.K. bearing USN 6SU20AO022 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms P A ARYA bearing USN 6SU20AO023 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms RITHIYA P T bearing USN 6SU20AO024 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms TINSON SABU bearing USN 6SU20AO025 has completed his/her internship at Aster MIMS, Kozhikode in the first Semester of the Anaesthesia and operation theatre technology programme for the academic year 2020-21.

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